

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Screening for duplicates in the germplasm collections

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Rice researchers in the tropics often have difficulty maintaining a large germplasm collection in limited storage facilities. Often the advice is to reject duplicates within a collection. Usually samples are discarded when two of them have similar names, identical grain features, identical maturity and other morphoagronomic features, and the same or neighboring places of origin.

Results from screening similarly named germplasm for BB and WBPH resistance.

Cultivar	Raipur accession no.	Reaction ^a	
		BB	WBPH
Badshahbhog	B54	S	S
Badshahbhog	B189	S	R
Badshahbhog	B220	S	S
Badshahbhog	B227	S	S
Badshahbhog	B236	S	S
Badshahbhog	B248	R	S
Badshahbhog	B466	S	S
Badshahbhog	B670	S	S
Badshahbhog	B799	S	S
Badshahbhog	B973	S	S
Badshahbhog	B1005	S	S
Badshahbhog	B1209	R	S
Badshahbhog	B1322	S	S
Badshahbhog	B1899	S	S
Bhata dudgi	B1627	S	S
Bhata dudgi	B2177	R	S
Chhatri	C90	S	S
Chhatri	C364	R	S
Dubraj	D12	S	R
Dubraj	D61	R	S
Dubraj	D341	S	S
Dubraj	D422	S	MR
Dubraj	D1026	S	R
Gurmatia	G123	S	R
Gurmatia	G185	S	R
Gurmatia	G245	S	S
Gurmatia deshi	G7	R	R
Jhilli	J107	S	R
Jhilli	J273	R	R
Jhilli	J274	R	MR
Jhilli	J388	S	R
Jhilli parag	J105	S	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

We have a collection of about 19,000 indigenous rice varieties, many with identical names. We screened a small sample of accessions with similar names, maturity, grain features, and origins for resistance to bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* and to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* at IRRI.

The results are presented in the table. Of the 14 accessions of Badshahbhog evaluated, B248 and B1209 were rated resistant to BB. B189 was found resistant to WBPH. Other accessions were susceptible to both. Other accessions having identical names (Bhata dudgi, Chhatri, Dubraj,

Gurmatia, and Jhilli) showed variable reactions to the pest and disease under study.

This study examined a small sample against only BB and WBPH. More variable reactions might be expected if the materials were evaluated for other traits and with various pathotypes or biotypes of diseases and pests. These results suggest that land races collected from different fields or villages that have identical names and morphoagronomic features may not have the same pest resistance. They should not be discarded from a collection before thorough evaluation. □

Breeding methods

Propagation of *Porteresia coarctata* using immature seeds

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P. coarctata Tateoka (n=48) (formerly *Oryza coarctata* Roxb.), a wild rice species native to the coastal regions of India and Bangladesh, abounds along the mouths of estuaries. Because it flourishes in highly saline water, it could be a source of genes for salt tolerance to transfer into cultivated rices.

Part of the problem with hybridization is that mature seeds of *P. coarctata* do not germinate. At IRRI, we have been limited to using runners and cuttings for propagation.

We experimented with different conditions for inducing germination of *P. coarctata* seeds. Mature seeds did not germinate, even after they were treated with varying concentrations of sodium chloride and the embryos excised and inoculated in Murashige and Skoog (MS) culture medium. However,

immature seeds (soft dough stage) germinated (average 90%) in both distilled water and 1/4 concentration MS medium.

Some germinated seeds failed to develop fully. Some lacked shoots or roots. Others dried up after emergence. Of 36 seeds that germinated, 12 plantlets survived and were transferred to Yoshida's water culture solution.

Propagating *P. coarctata* through immature seeds could be important in germplasm exchange, since immature seeds are more easily transported from place to place than runners or cuttings. □

Performance of anther-derived rice lines

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Seven anther-derived cultures from the F₁s of Vaigai/Co 40 (developed in a TNAU-Indian Agricultural Research

Institute collaboration) were tested in seven trials against check Co 43. Cultures 433A-R5 and 433A-R6 performed better than Co 43 during kar (Jul-Oct) season (8.8 and 11.4% yield increase) (see table).

Culture 433A-R6 was photoperiod

insensitive (duration 134–137 d); duration fluctuated 11–20 d in other cultures. All cultures are semidwarf (plant height 57–76 cm) and all have 6.9–7.7 panicles/hill. Grain in 6 cultures is short and bold; in 433A-R6, it is long and slender. Rice color is white.

Culture 433A-R1 is resistant to blast (Bl) and rice tungro virus (RTV); 433A-R5 is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to RTV and bacterial blight (BB); 433A-R6 is resistant to Bl and moderately resistant to RTV, BB, and brown spot. □

Performance of anther culture-derived rice lines at Coimbatore, India, 1982-83 to 1986-87.^a

Culture	Mean grain yield (t/ha)				Productivity (kg/d)	Duration (d)				Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	1000-grain wt (g)
	Kar	Cold weather	Navarai	Overall mean		Kar	Cold weather	Navarai	Mean			
433A-R1	5.2	4.5	5.9	5.2	37.1	141	148	132	140	76	7.1	19.6
433A-R2	5.0	4.5	5.5	5.0	35.8	136	150	132	139	72	7.3	20.9
433A-R3	5.3	4.1	4.8	4.8	34.1	139	151	134	141	75	7.7	19.4
433A-R4	5.2	4.2	5.5	5.0	35.8	138	151	132	140	69	6.9	19.0
433A-R5	5.4	4.9	5.8	5.4	38.6	137	152	132	140	75	7.5	18.8
433A-R6	5.6	4.6	5.7	5.3	39.1	137	136	134	136	57	7.3	19.0
433A-R7	5.1	4.8	4.7	4.9	34.9	138	149	134	140	76	7.1	19.0
Co 43 (check)	5.0	4.9	5.9	5.22	38.4	139	141	130	136	74	7.2	20.0

^aKar = Jul-Oct, navarai = Feb-Apr.

***Oryza nivara* sources of cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) in rice**

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Cytoplasmic diversity is an important problem in hybrid rice breeding and production. Only a few CMS sources are being used in China, making hybrid rice potentially vulnerable to a disease or insect epidemic.

To find new sources for hybrid rice breeding and to study the cytogenic interaction in *Oryza* spp., we have used *O. nivara* introduced from IRRI (acc. 101508 and 101466) as donors of CMS cytoplasm in crosses with one set of cultivars. So far, we have developed four CMS lines—Chao Yang 1A (indica), Zhen Shan 97A (indica), Nan Jin 56A (japonica), and Rei-Min A (japonica)—that have the cytoplasm of *O. nivara* acc. 101508.

Preliminary studies show no significant difference between Zhen Shan 97A (nivara cytoplasm) and Zhen Shan 97A (WA cytoplasm) in agrocharacter, floral characters, and pollen fertility (Table 1), and in cytogenic interaction (Table 2). The two

Table 1. Comparison of N-Zhen Shan 97A with W-Zhen Shan 97A. Puzhou, China, 1987.

CMS A-line	Days to 50% heading	Height (cm)	Panicle exertion (cm)	Exserted stigma (%)	Pollen fertility (%)	
					Typical abortive	Round abortive
N-Zhen Shan 97A	68.5	57.0	-6.1	25.9	92.1	7.9
W-Zhen Shan 97A	70.0	56.3	-5.8	24.1	89.3	10.7

Table 2. Pollen fertility of F₁ progenies.^a Hainan, China, 1988.

Male parent	Plants (no.)	Female parent								
		N-Zhen Shan 97A				W-Zhen Shan 97A				
		F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				
	F	PF	PS	CS		F	PF	PS	CS	
IR22	20	16	4	0	0	20	17	3	0	0
IR24	20	20	0	0	0	20	18	2	0	0
Ming 63	20	19	1	0	0	18	18	0	0	0
Taiyin 1	18	16	1	1	0	20	18	2	0	0
Milyang 46	20	18	2	0	0	20	19	1	0	0
IR46826B	20	0	0	3	17	20	0	0	2	18
IR46827B	20	0	0	1	19	20	0	0	1	19
IR46828B	20	0	0	4	16	20	0	0	2	18
Hong 410	20	0	3	13	4	20	0	4	12	4

^aPollen fertility classes: F = fertile, 91–100% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 51–90% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 6–50% pollen fertility; CS = completely sterile, 0–5% pollen fertility.

CMS sources seem to be genetically similar.

In a crossing experiment based on F₁ pollen fertility, IR22, IR24, Ming 63, Taiyin 1, IR1055, Yin Ni Ai He,

Milyang 23, and Milyang 46 were classified as effective restorers; Hong 410 as a partial maintainer; and IR46826B, IR46827B, and IR46828B as complete maintainers to both A-lines.